

Comparative RNA-expression meta-analysis of antennae and leg appendages in insects and the impact of distal-less (Dll) gene knockdown on appendages in (broad-horned flour beetle) *Gnathocerus cornutus*.

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Abstract

Phenotypic variations are often caused by changes in gene expression, while the developmental programs and signaling pathways remain well-preserved. This research emphasizes the concept of homologous structures. The study employs meta-analysis of transcriptome data and gene knockdown experiments to elucidate the genetic basis of appendage differentiation and specialization. The investigation develops into the differential gene expression and co-expression study of antennae and legs in three insect species, *Tribolium castaneum*, *Heliconius Melpomene*, and *Danaus plexipus*. A total of 371 genes were differentially expressed between antennae vs leg tissues across three species and a total of 278 differentially expressed genes were identified in between leg tissue comparisons in three species. Co-expression revealed associated network and hub genes for differentiation of leg and antennae. Gene Ontology (GO) analysis categorized the DEGs into biological processes, molecular function, and cellular components revealing antennae-specific heat sensing pathways and leg-specific muscular regulatory pathways. The KEGG pathway categorized oxidative phosphorylation as the most prominent pathway in leg tissue expression. Additionally, the study explored the functional significance of the highly conserved distal-less (dll) gene in appendage development in (broad-horned flour beetle) *Gnathocerus cornutus*. Leg structures were significantly reduced in the knockdown experiment. Overall, the findings have broader implications for understanding of regulatory network of appendage development and fields such as evolutionary biology and insect pest management.

1. Introduction

Serially homologous structures are repetitive organs on each segment and share a common ancestry, revealing similarities in their underlying anatomical composition despite serving different functions in diverse insect species [1]. Variations in size, and shape or number, of structures such as mouthparts, and legs have adapted to meet the specific needs of various ecological niches [2]. Adaptations from the slender wings of dragonflies enabling swift flight, to the robust mandibles of ants, facilitating efficient predation and nest construction, exemplify the incredible ingenuity of nature in producing an array of insect forms, each finely

tuned to their respective environments [3]. By studying the homologous structures among insects, researchers gain invaluable insights into the evolutionary processes that have sculpted these captivating creatures into the awe-inspiring diversity we observe today [4]. Phenotypic variations across species are often caused by evolutionary changes in gene expression and developmental programs [5]. Understanding the genetic basis of morphological diversity and specialization is paramount to unraveling the intricate mechanisms governing organismal development and evolution.

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Figure 1: illustrates the diversity of appendages in insects. Panel (A) represents a generalized depiction of butterfly appendages. Panel (B) provides a precise representation of the sexually dimorphic species *Gnathocerus cornutus* showcasing the male with an enlarged mandibular horn in contrast to the female lacking this exaggerated mandibular growth. Additionally, *Tribolium castaneum* males are depicted devoid of this particular trait.

Numerous studies concluded that the gene expression of homologous structures of unlike species exhibited more similarity than that of different morphological structures of the same species. It is an illustration of evolutionarily conserved transcriptional programs regulating the synthesis of significant proteins that characterize certain organs [6]. In this study, we are doing a meta-analysis of transcriptome expression for homologous structures (antennae vs legs) in three insect species. This expression analysis revealed important genes and signaling pathways involved in the diversification of serially homologous appendages. Our finding backs up the widely held idea that insect serially homologous structures are valuable models for morphological evolution even after millions of years of evolutionary separation. Among the myriad features that contribute to the remarkable diversity observed in the appendages like legs, antennae, and mandibles have gathered major interest due to their essential roles in diverse behaviors and ecological interactions. To shed light on the molecular underpinnings of appendage differentiation and function, comparative transcriptomic studies have been undertaken across species of varying evolutionary divergences, including *Danuas plexipus*, *Heliconius melpomene*, and *Tribolium castaneum*.

The butterfly species, *Danuas plexipus*, and *Heliconius melpomene* stand out as classic models in understanding the evolutionary implications of wing pattern diversification [7], which is crucial for species recognition and mate selection [8]. However, little is known about how these butterflies diverge in the molecular signaling controlling the differentiation of their antennae and legs, which might underpin specialized sensory functions and locomotion. *Tribolium castaneum*, on the other hand, is a widely

studied model organism in insect genetics and developmental biology [9]. The comparative RNA expression analysis of homologous appendages (antennae and legs) in *Tribolium castaneum* may provide valuable insight into identifying regulatory networks for differential differentiation in the beetle model.

We are aware of the fact that RNA-seq data may have numerous technical variables that could impact downstream analysis, for instance, we know library preparation protocol, sample isolation, age of the individual, dissections or other surrounding tissues, and diverse preservation techniques can influence such RNA-Seq data [10, 11]. We conducted a meta-analysis of three datasets, from the same Illumina HiSeq 3000 platform comprising tissues from the antennae and legs of three distinct insect species, to better understand the evolution of gene expression in these three species.

Lastly, we did a functional evaluation of the distal-less (*dll*) gene in sexually dimorphic *Gnathocerus cornutus* (broad-horned flour beetle) species. This beetle has been introduced as an excellent model for studying sexually dimorphic traits [12]. In this species, the male beetle has enlarged mandibular horn and the females have normal size mandibles [13]. Males use these mandibular horns for male-male-combat and to attract females [14]. We considered the role of the Distal-less (*dll*) gene in serially homologous appendages development [15]. *Dll* is a conserved homeobox transcription factor that determines the proximal-distal part of appendages like antennae,

DEGs to investigate enhanced canonical pathways. A Venn diagram displaying the number of DEGs from each species was made using the Venn 2.0 online tool.

Weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA)

Weighted gene co-expression network analysis was done using the WGCNA package in R [Langfelder, 2008]. A gene co-expression network (WGCNA) is composed of gene expression profiles represented as nodes and gene connections that arise when two genes are significantly co-expressed. Strongly linked genes or genes with close relationships create modules. The first main element of a module is called a module eigengene and it is indicative of the gene expression profiles found in that module. The first primary component accounts for the biggest amount of diversity among genes. A soft threshold was employed in the network construction process to provide a link weight to every pair of genes in a weighted network and a hard threshold is used to define unweighted network connections.

Gene Enrichment Analysis

Gene enrichment analysis was performed on the differentially expressed genes to determine their biological activities and ontology. The GO analysis was carried out by the IDEP web tool [23]. GO terms with FDR value ≤ 0.05 were screened for differentially expressed gene enrichment. The enrichment was categorized into biological functions, molecular functions, and cellular components. We conducted a pathway analysis by mapping all the DEGs according to their biological activities. A highly enriched route with a p-value of less than 0.05 was identified.

Analysis

Computational work was done by writing shell scripts and submitting jobs on a High-throughput computer cluster at the Max Planck Institute, in Germany. The results produced were further analyzed on a personal laptop and lab computers. Statistics and visualization were done on program R; the package used was described in the script file. The weighted gene correlation network analysis package (WGCNA), which was created especially for evaluating big high-dimensional genomic datasets, was used to perform statistical analyses [24]. WGCNA was used to create various plots, network building, module detection, topological overlap matrix creation, and more (Figure 12 – Figure 16). The network visualizations were created using Cytoscape website. Gene ontology web was also used. Other software, like Imagej, and Zeiss Zenlite, were used for morphometric analysis.

Knockdown candidate genes (dsRNA synthesis for RNAi)

For the RNA interference (RNAi) studies, the knockdown target gene's double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) was created. The cloning of the target gene served as the initial step. Dll (Distal-less) of *G. cornutus* were cloned, and dsRNA was processed into siRNAs (short interference) [25].

In-silico analysis

Genes of interest were obtained from the database (FlyBase

and ibeetle) for homolog sequence. The whole RNA expression data file of *Gnathocerus cornutus* was obtained from our collaborator. Yasukazu Okada, Tokyo University, Japan, and blasted. Primers were designed for obtained sequences of *Gnathocerus cornutus* for conserved sequences of isoforms by using Genious prime. Primers were synthesized for each gene of interest in upstream and downstream regions to rule out off-target effects. Primer pairs are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Primers pair for Distal-less (Dll), up (Upstream), and Tail (Downstream) fragments.

NAME	SEQUENCE	Fragment length	Tm
Dll_Up_1F	AGTTCTCGCGAAAC CCTTCC	680	56°C
Dll_up_1R	GTTCCCAGCGACA GGATAC		
Dll_up_2F	ACGAGCGTTTCTCA AGTCGT	678	60°C
Dll_up_2R	AACCCAGCAACCT ATACACC		
Dll_Tail_1F	GCGCTGCCTTCATC ATCTC	750	-
Dll_tail_1R	AGCAGTGGTATCAA CGCAGA		
Dll_Tail_2F	ACTGCGTCCTTTGA AATCGC	750	60°C
Dll_tail_2R	TACCGTAAATTGCC CCACCG		

cDNA synthesis

cDNA library was established following the isolation of total RNA from the head region, primers were utilized to amplify the requisite gene segments. The synthesis of cDNA was conducted utilizing the Zymogen kit following the manufacturer's guidelines.

dsRNA preparation (In-vitro-transcription)

Proceeded with 500ng enough plasmid using the T7 Ambion Megascript Kit. Kept at 37°C on the block for 4-5 hours (not overnight). Kept at 37°C on the block for 4-5 hours in a reaction mixture.

Injection Procedure

The injection was prepared according to 1µg/µl. Injected mature larvae, which were slightly darker and long in size. But not pre-pupae (motionless). Prepared the injection apparatus (as recommended by lab protocol) and should be oriented at an angle of ~60. Petri-dish-containing larvae were placed on ice. Prepared a micro-slide with a double side tap (to fix larvae). Place the cooled larvae's lateral side on the tape using insect forceps. The needle penetrated to the lateral abdomen side where a thin cuticle separates the stronger ventral and dorsal cuticle. (Observed larvae stretching). Larvae were carefully removed from the tape by using forceps and placed in dry petri plates at room temperature. After that, place in a vial containing whole-grain flour.

Negative control where also injected with a buffer solution.

Gene Module Identification

The establishment of the network involves the identification of modules. Modules refer to clusters comprising closely interconnected nodes, specifically genes characterized by elevated topological overlap. Empirical evidence suggests that a weighted topological overlap measure yields a greater number of interconnected modules compared to an unweighted measure [26]. Identification of the gene module was done using the weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) program which uses unsupervised clustering approaches utilizing a dissimilarity metric grounded in the Topological Overlap Matrix (TOM), we executed an average linkage hierarchical cluster procedure through the R standard function “hclust”. The resulting modules are shown as branches within a dendrogram, and the partitioning is executed through the dynamic hybrid tree-cut algorithm [24]. A topological overlap matrix (TOM) plot characterized by color-coded elements, functions as a visual synopsis of a co-expression network providing clarity on the values present within the dissimilarity matrix. The hierarchical clustering dendrogram dictates the arrangement

of rows and columns in the plot, with red and yellow hues indicating instances of both low and high dissimilarity correspondingly (refer to Figure 16). The modules manifest as red squares strategically positioned along the diagonal axis. It is imperative to note the inherent symmetry of TOM plots along the diagonal, as a consequence of their graphical manifestation of the symmetric Topological Overlap Matrix.

3. Results and Discussion

The alignment rate with the reference genome for each respective species varied between 88% and 98%. The principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted, which resulted in the separation of samples based on both species and tissue specificity (Figure 3). Samples were separated by species and tissues.

This step ensures the reliability and consistency of the subsequent differential gene expression analysis. We found the serially homologous structures within species are more similar than between species.

Identification of DEGs

Our meta-analysis revealed intriguing patterns of differential gene expression (DEG) between the antennae and legs within

Figure: 3. (A) The second and third principal component separates the tissues for each species. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) among comparisons. (B) DEGs between Antennae vs Leg within each species, (Tissues_Antennae-species_heliconiusmelpomene)-Antennae and leg tissues of *Heliconius melpomene*, (Tissues_Antennae-Species_Danusplexipus)-differentially expressed genes between leg and antennae of *Danus plexipus*. (Antennae-leg)-differentially expressed genes between leg and antennae of *Tribolium castaneum* (C) Venn diagram for DEGs between leg and antennae within each species.

each species. To understand the expression pattern of genes between three insect species, pairwise comparisons were made using the *deseq2* package on R. A p -value ≤ 0.05 threshold was set to retrieve the significant DEGs between antennae vs legs within each species. Furthermore, DEGs were also identified for leg tissues across species. A total of 615 differentially expressed genes were identified between the antennae vs legs tissues of *Heliconius molpomene*, with 46.99% (289 genes) being upregulated in antennae and 56% (326 genes) upregulated in legs. 587 DEGs in *Dannaus pelxipus* leg and antennae comparison in which 374 genes were downregulated, and 213 genes were upregulated. A total of 597 DEGs were identified between antennae vs leg tissues of *Tribolium castaneum* in which 264 genes were downregulated and 333 genes were upregulated (Figure 4A). 381 DEGs were common between the two butterfly species, while 421 and 415 DEGs were shared between *H. molpomene* and *T. castaneum* and *D. pelxipus* and *T. castaneum*, respectively. A total of 371 DEGs were found to be common among three comparisons (Figure 4B).

Functional annotation (Antennae vs Legs comparison)

Figure 6: Common biological functions enrichment of DEGs in Antennae vs leg tissues comparison within in each species (A) Upregulated DEGs in Leg tissues and downregulated in antennae tissues (B) Upregulated differentially expressed genes antennae tissues and downregulated in leg tissues.

The comparison of gene expression between the antennae and legs of the three species reveals interesting differences in the functional pathways associated with these two tissues. Comparison between tissues of antennae and legs shows overall similar patterns in each species.

Upregulated pathways in antennae

Upregulated pathways in antennae were found to be downregulated in leg tissues. For instance, processes related to Protein refolding (GO:0042026): The significant upregulation of protein refolding in antennae suggests a higher demand for protein quality control mechanisms. This may be related to the antennae's sensory functions, where precise protein folding is critical for proper receptor function

and signal transduction. The upregulation of cilium assembly (GO:0060271) and organization (GO:0044782) indicates an increased formation and maintenance of cilia in the antennae. Cilia are essential for sensory processes, and their upregulation suggests their involvement in specific sensory functions of the antennae. The regulation of plasma membrane bonded cell projection assembly (GO:0120031) and cell projection assembly (GO:0030031) points towards the formation of various cell projections including cilia, which are likely to be essential for the sensory functions of the antennae. Response to heat (Go:0009408) and response to temperature stimulus (Go:0009266): The antennae show a strong response to heat and temperature stimuli indicating their role in thermal sensation this response is crucial for detecting environmental temperature changes and guiding the behavior of the insect {González-Tokman, 2020}.

Downregulated Pathways in Antennae and upregulated in legs Skeletal muscle contraction (Go:0003009), Striated muscle contraction (Go:0006941), Multicellular organismal movement (Go:0050879), Muscular movement (Go:0050881) and neuromuscular process (Go:0050879) the

down-regulation of these muscles related pathways in antennae and up-regulation of all these pathways in legs suggests that antennae tissues are not involved in direct movement or muscular contraction this supports the idea that the antennae are primary sensory organs rather than locomotor appendages {Krishnan, 2015}.

Comparative transcriptome (leg tissues)

Additionally in the second comparison, we identified differentially expressed genes between legs across three species. A sum of 1463 genes were downregulated and 1717 genes were up-regulated between *Tribolium castaneum* vs *Heliconius Melpomene*. 971 genes were down-regulated and 1215 genes were upregulated in the comparison between

Figure 6: A Venn diagram depicting the subset of genes exhibiting differential expression within the leg tissue in interspecies comparative analysis. (A) Among the upregulated differentially expressed genes in three comparative analyses of species, 135 genes exhibited common upregulation. (B) Concerning downregulated differentially expressed genes in three species comparison 143 common genes demonstrated downregulation. Differentially expressed genes across species comparison, Tc_leg-mel_leg: A sum of 1717 genes were up-regulated and 1463 genes were down-regulated in *Tribolium castaneum_vs_Heliconius Melpomene* comparison. *Danaus_leg_Tc_leg*: A sum of 1215 genes were up-regulated and 971 genes were down-regulated in *Danaus plexipus_vs_Tribolium castaneum* comparison, *danaus_leg_mel_leg*: A sum of 1955 genes were up-regulated and 1463 gene were down-regulated in *Danaus plexipus_vs_Heliconius melpomene* comparison.

Danaus vs Tribolium leg tissues. A total of 1463 genes were downregulated and the 1955 gene was upregulated between *Danaus vs Melp*. A Venn diagram of differentially expressed genes between legs appendages is shown in Figure 8. 135 upregulated genes and 143 down-regulated genes were shared in all three comparisons.

Functional annotation of DEGs in leg tissues.

We delved into the functional annotations associated with specific Gene Ontology (GO) terms for DEGs within the leg tissues (inter-species comparison).

Upregulated Pathways

GO:0034645 - Cellular macromolecule biosynthetic Process (Upregulated): This GO term indicates an upregulation in the biosynthesis of cellular macromolecules in *Tribolium castaneum* legs compared to *Heliconius melpomene*. Increased macromolecule biosynthesis could signify higher demands for cellular growth, development, or tissue repair in legs, possibly related to their unique physiological or ecological requirements.

Cellular protein metabolic process (Go: 0044267) upregulated, the observed upregulating of this pathway in *Tribolium castaneum* indicates heightened activity in protein metabolism in comparison to *Heliconius melpomene*. This means there is a higher demand for protein turnover which could linked to adaptations like reactions to environmental stimuli or differences in the ecological role of legs in two species, for example *T. castaneum* does not fly as *Heliconius melpomene* so *T. castaneum* has more intensive walking and foraging role via legs than butterfly.

Upregulation of the organonitrogen computed biosynthesis process (GO:1901566) shows the increased activity in the biosynthesis of this pathway in leg tissues indicating *Tribolium castaneum*. These substances are required for a variety of biochemical activities that involve amino acid nucleotides and other molecules. This raises the possibility of species-specific differences in nitrogen metabolism. Upregulation of translation processes (Go:0006412) in leg tissues of *Tribolium castaneum* exhibits an increased process

Figure 9: Depicts the enrichment of biological processes in leg tissue because of inter-species comparisons, while downregulation represents the opposite. (A) Biological processes that are enriched for upregulated differentially expressed genes in *Danaus plexipus* when compared to *Heliconius melpomene* (B) biological processes that are enriched for upregulated differentially expressed genes in *Danaus plexipus* when compared to *Tribolium castaneum* (C) biological processes that are enriched for upregulated differentially expressed genes in *Tribolium castaneum* when compared to *Heliconius melpomene*.

of protein synthesis. This increased translational activity could be linked to distinct developmental processes, tissue remodeling, or *T.castaneum* species-specific response to its ecological cues.

Downregulated pathways

Carbohydrate derivative catabolic process (Go:1901136): The reduced catabolic activity linked to carbohydrate derivatives in *Tribolium castaneum* that have essential roles in both cellular signaling and energy consumption. This differential gene expression also indicates the two species differ in how they use energy and process nutrients. Biological regulation (Go:0065007) comparison between *T. castaneum* and *H. melpomene* observed the downregulation of biological regulation in the legs of former species which indicates the difference in regulatory mechanism controlling cellular process. This GO term is involved in various cellular functions such as response to external stimuli and homeostasis.

Go:0050789 - downregulated regulation of biological process: this gene ontology (go) phrase refers to a broad class of genes that control many biological processes. the observed downregulation could point to differences between *Heliconius melpomene* and *Tribolium castaneum's* regulatory networks controlling biological processes in their legs.

Anatomical Structure Development (Downregulated):

O:0048856 The downregulation of anatomical structure development in *Tribolium castaneum* legs could indicate that the two species have different tissue or organ development. This could be due to anatomical differences or functional modifications in their legs.

Comparative Transcriptomic Analysis (merging same tissues)

To find the core genes that differentiate legs and antennae, we expect some overlap of the genes found through this approach and the 371 DEGs shared in the analysis above. This should be tested. In this analysis, leg, and antennae tissues from three distinct species were amalgamated into unified groups, and a differential expression analysis was performed to assess the ensuing outcomes. A significance threshold of p-value<0.01 was established to identify DEGs within both tissue types to further restrict the false discovery. The examination revealed comparable biological significance in pathways, wherein pivotal genes, as determined by their log-fold changes, were visually represented in Figure 10. Whole list of DEGs in this comparison is provided in table 07 in appendices. Moreover, network analysis distinctly demarcated networks based on tissue-specific functions and ecological roles. This comprehensive evaluation provides insights into the nuanced molecular distinctions between the

Figure 10: Scatterplot for differentially expressed genes between leg and antennae tissues p-value<0.01, genes with log fold change > 0.8, green color genes are down-regulated in leg tissues while genes in red colors are downregulated in leg. tissues.

Figure 11: The biological functional network herein is characterized by interconnected pathways, with nodes established based on a criterion of gene set overlap exceeding 30%, a parameter subject to adjustment. Pathways are denoted in green and red to signify up- and down-regulation, respectively. Nodes of greater darkness indicate gene sets that are more significantly enriched, while larger nodes correspond to larger gene sets. The thickness of edges corresponds to the degree of gene overlap between interconnected pathways.. tissues.

examined leg and antennae tissues across diverse species. The network analysis of biological functions unveiled the functional roles of prominent genes within two distinct networks. The first network encompassed processes integral to plasma-membrane bounded cell projection assembly, intracellular transport, cilium assembly, microtubule-based activities, cilium organization, and cell projection organization. Notably, these interconnected biological functions exhibited a down-regulated pattern in the examined leg tissues. Conversely, an opposing trend was observed in the antennae tissues, where the same network demonstrated an upregulation.

The second network was characterized by functions associated with locomotion and movement, including control of muscular system functions, skeletal muscle contraction, musculoskeletal movement, regulation of striated muscle contraction, multicellular organism movement, and muscular contraction. Importantly, these functions exhibited interconnectivity and were discerned to be enriched within the set of DEGs identified between the leg and antennae tissues. This comprehensive analysis sheds light on the nuanced regulatory mechanisms governing diverse biological functions within these distinct tissue types.

WGCNA (Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis)

Before analysis, the data underwent a normalization process. Subsequently, both genes and samples were subjected to scrutiny to identify and address instances of excessive missing values. Genes characterized by a notable prevalence of missing values were systematically excluded, resulting in a curated set of 6000 genes for further investigation. Following

this, to find possible outliers in the samples, a dendrogram was created using average linkage hierarchical clustering methods (Figure 12). Posterior to standardizing the connectivity, a single sample was identified as an outlier, prompting its exclusion from all subsequent analyses.

Figure 12: (A) Scale independence, (B) mean conductivity.

Adhering to the scale-free topology criteria, a soft thresholding power (β) of 18 was selected to effectively estimate the scale-free network topology, yielding an $RR2$ value of 0.811. Figure 13A shows the model fit $RR2$ for the scale-free topology over various candidate soft threshold powers. Moreover, the mean connectivity concerning the different candidate soft threshold powers is shown in Figure 13B.

Figure 13: (A) Scale independence, (B) mean conductivity.

The dendrogram produced by gene clustering is shown in Figure 14, along with the associated color-coded module memberships. A minimum module size requirement of 30 and a maximum block size restriction of 6000 genes were used to identify modules. When the cut height was less than 0.25, similar modules were combined. The dynamic hybrid tree cut technique was used to calculate the cut height. Eight modules are listed in Table 8, with the red module having 41 genes and the grey module having 391 genes as examples.

Table 8. Summary of module assignments.

Module Color	Total Gene Assign
black	29
blue	849
brown	819
green	495
grey	391
red	41
turquoise	2482
yellow	521

Figure 14. Gene dendrogram. Colors along the bottom indicate module assignments. (B) Eigengene Dendrogram. The (grey), and red modules are highly related.

A heatmap depicting network topological overlap, derived from dissimilarity measures based on the Topological Overlap Matrix (TOM), has been generated. The resultant TOM plot, inclusive of a dendrogram and color-coded module memberships, is presented in Figure 15. It is discernible that as genes converge in the clustering, the corresponding heatmap color lightens, indicative of heightened topological overlap. The definition of modules involves a branch cut height, where genes located towards the terminal end of a branch exhibit a greater likelihood of belonging to their assigned module compared to genes positioned higher in the dendrogram. The latter genes are characterized by a higher module membership. The magnitude of module membership demonstrates a

Figure 15. Presents a Network Heatmap Plot encompassing all genes, where each row and column corresponds to an individual gene. Light red hues in the heatmap imply significant topological overlap, while dark colors show low topological overlap. Interestingly, various modules are defined by luminous squares along the diagonal. The corresponding gene dendrogram is located along the corresponding axes and includes module assignments.

notably strong positive correlation with intramodular connectivity, as evidenced by a high positive linear association observed within the red module (refer to Figure 16). Broadly, a heightened module membership is indicative of increased intramodular connectivity. Genes possessing both characteristics emerge as potential hub gene candidates of significance. Since the absolute values of intramodular connection and module membership exhibit a strong correlation, both metrics can be useful in identifying putative hub genes.

Figure 16: (A) The Red module is the most significantly associated with a biological role in leg tissues. The module-trait relationship is discerned through the examination of correlations between distinct modules and traits. Various colors on the left side signify distinct modules MEgrey, MEred, METurquoise, MEblue, MEgreen, MEblack, MEBrown, and on the right side, the scale of the correlation coefficient (r) is presented. Each column corresponds to a specific trait with each cell denoting the respective correlation. A negative value indicates a negative correlation. (B) A high gene significance and module membership in red genes indicate that the expression of a gene has a good correlation with the trait. (C) Red module expression counts for each sample. (D) Mean normalized count expression difference of red module between leg and antennae tissues.

Figure 17: Genes within the red module are interconnected based on their correlation, identifying them as central or hub genes.

The grey, red, and black modules are positively related in the leg and negatively correlated in the antennae, we found a good association of some important modes such as the red module to further investigate and compare with differential gene expression analysis. Crucial modules were examined through a web chart to identify the most strongly interconnected genes and the relationships they have. As a

result, network data was exported from R and shown using Cytoscape, a specialist tool for illustrating biological networks. [27]. Figure 17 showcases a network highlighting highly connected hub genes within the red modules. Concurrently, Table 9 illustrates hub genes enriched with pathway information. Table 09. Hub genes, identified within pathways, exhibit enrichment specific to the *Tribolium castaneum*

model species by the Enrichment FDR values and the number of genes (nGenes) associated with each pathway.

Table 09. Hub genes, identified within pathways, exhibit enrichment specific to the *Tribolium castaneum* model species by the Enrichment FDR values and the number of genes (nGenes) associated with each pathway

Enrichment FDR	nGenes	Pathway	Genes
2.92E-07	4	Mixed, incl. troponin, and myosin tail	TC001048 TC011461 TC011769 TC012704
0.00092073	2	Myosin tail, and Troponin	TC011461 TC011769
5.98E-08	5	Mixed, incl. myosin tail, and troponin	TC001048 TC011461 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
7.23E-09	6	Mixed, incl. ef-hand domain, and myosin tail	TC001048 TC006493 TC011461 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
2.21E-09	7	Mixed, incl. myosin. large ATPases., and of hand	TC001048 TC006493 TC006656 TC011461 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
2.00E-05	4	EF-hand	TC006493 TC006656 TC012196 TC012704
2.06E-06	5	EF-hand domain pair	TC006493 TC006656 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
3.25E-07	6	EF-hand, calcium-binding motif	TC001048 TC006493 TC006656 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
0.03188937	2	EGF-like domain	TC008043 TC011508
1.50E-06	6	EF-hand domain	TC001048 TC006493 TC006656 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
1.74E-05	5	EF-Hand 1, calcium-binding site	TC006493 TC006656 TC011769 TC012196 TC012704
0.03764026	2	SET domain	TC005968 TC006184
0.03764026	2	SET(Su(var) 3-9-Zeste Enhancer, Trithorax)domain	TC005968 TC006181
3.25E-07	7	Calcium	TC006493 TC006656 TC008043 TC011769 TC012196 TC012671 TC012704
0.04339983	2	EGF domain, unclassified subfamily	TC008043 TC011508

Dll gene knockdown

Distal-less knockdown effects on appendages were observed in the broad-horned flour beetle *Gnathocerus cornutus*. The results revealed noticeable changes in leg morphology but no change in mandibles and antennae. The most prominent alteration observed was the absence of tarsals 1-4, (figure 19) indicating that distal-less knockdown had influenced the leg structures; this was the consistent result across the experimental group. In contrast to the influence on mandibles and but may have an effect on shape and functionality of antennae which was not clear in our experiment and need to be further investigated as there are some individual which have few numbers of antennae segments but this observation was not consistent.

We confirm distal-less has almost no role in proximal structures. The mandibles maintained their typical of same size, suggesting that the knockdown did not have a noticeable impact on this aspect of the *G. cornutus* appendage anatomy but functionality of mandibles need to be evaluated further. A significant mean size difference was observed in tibia length between Distal-less knockdown and controls with p-value < 3.98e-09. This finding supports the notion that distal-less knockdown specifically targets the proximal appendage-related genetic pathways in the insect. It is possible that the knockdown treatment primarily affects leg-related genes while having limited or no effect on the genetic pathways associated with mandible development. More research is

Figure 18: Presents network of enrichment results for various pathways for hub genes of red module in the *Tribolium castaneum* species, Notable pathways include those related to muscle function, such as "Mixed, incl. troponin, and myosin tail" and "Myosin tail, and Troponin," with specific genes (TC001048, TC011461, TC011769) contributing to these enrichments as were found in differential expression. Additionally, the table highlights enrichments in pathways associated with calcium-binding motifs (EF-hand, calcium-binding motif) and distinct domains like "SET domain" and "EGF-like domain," providing insights into molecular processes within the species.

required to understand the disparity in the regulatory role of distal-less (dll) to scrutinize the mechanisms that give rise to affect restricted, exclusively to leg-specific effects we observed no effect on appendages like mandibles or mandibular horn.

Understanding of molecular and functional diversification that underlies these homologous appendages is the goal of this research. Many pathways were overexpressed in antennae compared to legs indicating its specialized role as sensory organs. The overexpression biological pathways like the protein refolding pathway (GO:0042026), suggest its

Figure 19: Distalless (dll) gene knockdown experiment. (A) Dll_RNAi knockdown first leg, an arrow indicating reduction in length of the tibia (B) Normal first leg of *Gnathocerus cornutus* with normal tibia. (C) dll_RNAi knockdown complete insect body. (D) A normal individual with 1mm bar length. (E) The mean difference with T-test, no significant change in femur length, mandibular horn length, and mandibular horn width was observed. A significant difference was observed in tibia length between Distal-less knockdown and Controls with p-value < 3.98e-09.

4. Discussion

Homologous appendages (legs, antennae, mandibles, horn) were investigated in different insect species (*Tribolium castaneum*, *Heliconius melpomene*, *Danaus plexippus*, and *Gnathocerus cornutus*). Three of them (*Heliconius melpomene*, *Danaus plexippus*, and *Tribolium castaneum*) were investigated for comparative RNA-expression analysis for serially homologous appendage tissues: legs and antennae. Then Eventually we investigated the developmental role of homeobox transcription factor distal-less gene in sexually dimorphic exaggerated size of mandibular horn in *Gnathocerus cornutus* and its homologous appendages.

function in maintaining appropriate protein structure and functions is particularly significant. Pathways related to cilium organization (GO:0044782) and cilium assembly (GO:0060271) provide insight into processes of cilia growth that are typically associated with sensory perception. The pathways cell-projection assembly (GO:0030031) and the plasma membrane bounded-cell projection assembly (Go:0120031) propose the creation of cellular projections, enabling contact with the surroundings. Reflection of their function in temperature sensing, the antennae also exhibited enhanced response to heat (GO:0009408) and response to temperature stimulus (Go:009266). Intriguingly certain

energy, thereby prompting the upregulation of oxidative phosphorylation in leg tissues. here we recognized different tissues within an organism and we observed escalation in oxidative phosphorylation in insect leg tissues may signify a tissue-specific regulatory mechanism. This regulatory response is directed towards meeting the high demand associated with locomotion and multifaceted functions inherent to insect legs.

WGCNA (Weighted Gene-Co-Expression-Network Analysis)

The study involved a weighted gene-Co-expression-network analysis (WGCNA) conducted on leg and antennae tissues derived from three insect species to investigate regulatory pathways associated with specific biological traits. To differentiate between true biological pathways and possible noise sources like technical artifacts, trial errors, or false-positive results, co-expression modules that were clarified through hierarchical clustering were evaluated. The robustness of module-eigengene detection, which depends on highly connected intramodular hub genes, demonstrated robustness even in the presence of peripheral genes that may not truly belong to a given module. While hierarchical clustering served as a valuable exploratory method without the need for a priori information on cluster numbers, its propensity to generate clusters regardless of the existence of biologically relevant gene or eigengene groups was acknowledged.

The central element in gene-co-expression networks the module-eigengene served as a cornerstone with its definition as the first principal component indicating that if a module-eigengene exhibited biologically significant actions, most genes within that module likely functioned similarly. WGCNA, akin to Principal Component Analysis (PCA), offered a biologically motivated data reduction technique, distinguishing itself by allowing for component interdependency. Modules, potentially representing biological pathways, precluded the assumption of independence between them. An eigengene correlation network facilitated the examination of intermodular relationships, revealing the grouping of certain modules into meta-modules.

Eigengene networks displayed through average-linkage-hierarchical-clustering illustrated the existence of meta-modules, such as Module 1 (Brown, Black, and Green) and Module 2 (Red, Grey, Blue, and Turquoise). The identification of hub genes involved two methods: intramodular connectivity and TOM-based connectivity followed by network mapping. While most modules exhibited consistency between the two methods, certain discrepancies were noted, particularly in larger modules. The study acknowledged limitations, including the absence of external trait information for additional analyses and the challenge of determining whether modules should be treated individually or combined into meta-modules. The selection of candidate hub genes involved assessing their significance,

with preference given to those supported by gene ontology information. Comparisons between module significance and gene significance guided the identification of modules of interest.

This network analysis provided a foundation for generating research hypotheses, designing experiments, and validating candidate hub genes within biologically significant modules. The study outlined potential avenues for further investigation, emphasizing the importance of integrating gene ontology information and acknowledging the complexities inherent in module delineation and the selection of hub genes. Finally, the overlapping significantly associated genes with biological traits in the WGCNA analysis red module and differentially expressed genes were screened and checked for their biological role and associated function in the literature.

The identification of hub genes linked to tissue-specific differentiation in both antennae and leg tissues provides important information about the molecular processes controlling the growth and differentiation of various insect anatomical features. The elucidation of the roles and characteristics of the highlighted genes contributes to an enhanced understanding of their potential ecological significance and functional differentiation.

Troponin c (TC012196) and troponin c, isoform 2 (TC012704): these genes encode troponin c, a pivotal regulatory protein in muscle contraction. their presence signifies a critical role in the development and maintenance of muscle tissues in both antennae and legs. Nidogen-2-like protein (TC008043): associated with basement membrane assembly, the presence of this gene suggests a potential role in providing structural support and integrity to tissues, thereby contributing to the development of antennae and leg structures. Protein msta, isoform a-like (TC005968): the function of this protein may be linked to specific cellular processes, indicating a role in the differentiation of cells within antennae and leg tissues. Tropomyosin-2-like protein (TC011461): involved in the regulation of muscle contraction, the presence of tropomyosin underscores its significance in the development and function of muscle-related structures in both tissues. Zinc finger protein 585b-like (TC010415): zinc finger proteins, known for their regulatory roles in gene expression, may contribute to the differentiation of antennae and leg tissues through involvement in transcriptional regulation. myogenic-determination protein-like (TC015855): associated with myogenesis, this protein may play a part in the differentiation and maturation of muscle cells in the tissues of the legs and antennae. Calponin (TC000431) and calmodulin-like protein (TC006656): these proteins control the contraction of smooth muscles, and calmodulin, calcium-binding proteins also indicate potential roles in calcium signaling and muscle function, thereby contributing to tissue development.

Calcium-transporting ATPase (tc012671): this gene's association with calcium transport emphasizes the importance of calcium dynamics in cellular processes within antennae and leg tissues. Myosin regulatory light chain 2-like (TC011769): encoding a regulatory subunit of myosin, this gene further underscores the involvement of myosin-related processes in tissue differentiation and development.

Distal-less (Dll) knockdown

This specific genetic pathway involving distal-less potentially contributes to sexual dimorphism in mandibular appendages; however, we did not discern a direct involvement of distal-less (dll) in the exaggerated growth of sexually dimorphic traits. Distal-less may not be directly implicated in the development of mandibular appendages in *Gnathocerus cornutus*. Nonetheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that distal-less is well-recognized for its substantial role in appendage development across diverse organisms, including insects. Our findings support the role of distal-less in evolutionary selection, and no significant role in sexual selection these two mechanisms have different purposes and different molecular mechanisms [28]. The absence of a definitive role for distal-less in *Gnathocerus cornutus* mandibles underscores the intricacy and diversity of genetic networks and regulatory mechanisms governing appendage development in this species. The observed lack of tarsals in both males and females following distal-less knockdown suggests that distal-less regulates leg development irrespective of sex. The association between the dll gene and the Wingless and Int-1 (Wnt) signaling pathway lies in their concerted roles in embryonic patterning and tissue development. Wnt signaling makes a concentration gradient of signaling molecular guiding the expression of genes like distal-less and contributes to the precise cell types and tissues to respond specifically. The cross-talk between this complex regulation is crucial for proper structure formation of tissue boundaries during embryonic development.

5. Conclusion

We investigated gene expression patterns in antennae and leg tissues across diverse insect species. Antennae with heightened sensory functions and legs beyond locomotion exhibit species-specific adaptations demanding increased energy. Hub genes such as troponin-c underscore the tissue-specific differentiation while the distal-less gene highlights its role in the development and natural selection but not in sexually selected traits. These insights contribute to a nuanced understanding of insect biology and emphasize the interplay between genetic and ecological adaptation in shaping appendage structures.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendices

Table 7: Differentially expressed genes in leg tissues

Group	Ensembl id	Entrez gene id	Description
Upregulated	TC000461	103315208	Major-facilitator-superfamily domain-containing protein 6 like Protein
	TC000586	100142412	
	TC000608	658563	Carbonic anhydrase 7-like Protein
	TC001149	662212	Ras-related protein Rab-3-like Protein
	TC001360	662789	Catenin alpha-like Protein
	TC002140	656713	Cysteine-rich PDZ-binding protein-like Protein
	TC002241	103314837	
	TC002926	663957	
	TC003798	660036	
	TC004766	658640	Brain peptide IDL-like protein
	TC005412	657825	Beta-glucuronidase
	TC005765	103313947	
	TC006533	656781	Glucose dehydrogenase
	TC007349	664372	Arylsulfatase I-like Protein
	TC008742	664606	Intraflagellar transport protein 52 homolog-like Protein
	TC008966	659794	Insulinoma-associated protein 1a-like Protein
	TC009218	656114	Bardet-Biedl syndrome 2 protein homolog
	TC009519	656952	Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein K-like Protein
	TC009594	656281	Ring canal kelch protein-like Protein
	TC010663	655564	Dynein light chain 2, cytoplasmic-like Protein
	TC011177	656492	ELMO domain-containing protein 1-like Protein
	TC0111	656072	Intraflagellar transport protein 46

	79		homolog-like Protein
	TC011201	658020	Transmembrane protein 181-like Protein
	TC011508	660207	
	TC011548	659491	Cyclin-dependent kinase 1-like Protein
	TC012519	100142013	
	TC012520	656540	
	TC013763	103312939	
	TC014014	660233	Calcyphosin-like protein
	TC014031	661678	Potassium/Sodium transporting-ATPase subunit-beta 2like-Protein
	TC014033	103312937	Potassium/sodium transporting-ATPase subunit-beta-2-like Protein
	TC014251	655603	Cyclic-nucleotide gated cation channel subunit-A like Protein
	TC015024	107398087	Spectrin beta chain-like Protein
	TC015127	661975	Odorant receptor
	TC015323	661101	Serine/threonine-protein kinase BRSK2-like Protein
	TC015329	660360	Sodium/nucleoside cotransporter 2-like Protein
	TC015439	654996	Calmodulin-like Protein
	TC015879	655569	
	TC031275	662272	Centrosomal protein of 162 kDa-like Protein
	TC032630	100141621	
	TC032990	658724	Phosphate transporter
	TC034087	655007	Facilitated-trehalose-transporter_Tret1-2 homolog-like protein
	TC034435	662355	
	TC035050	664564	Glucosylceramidase
Downregulated	TC000228	659444	Myosin-light chain-kinase, smooth muscle-like protein
	TC000431	659621	Calponin
	TC001352	662397	
	TC002497	659511	Tachykinin-like peptides receptor 86C
	TC003094	659759	Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase-E(Z) like protein
	TC003326	656991	Actin-87E-like Protein
	TC003873	655757	Glutathione S-transferase omega-1-like Protein
	TC004000	661414	Cytosol aminopeptidase-like Protein
	TC004001	100141571	NADH dehydrogenase
	TC004591	660639	Voltage dependent-calcium channel subunit alpha 2/delta 3 like Protein
	TC004701	657463	Sarcalumenin-like Protein
	TC004956	657780	
	TC004962	658559	Isocitrate dehydrogenase
	TC005012	656552	cAMP-dependent protein kinase 1

	TC005572	659661	TGF-beta activated kinase 1
	TC005725	663732	Aconitate hydratase, mitochondrial
	TC005968	655294	Protein msta, isoform A-like Protein
	TC006159	662383	Protein msta, isoform A-like Protein
	TC006181	654885	
	TC006184	655216	
	TC006372	662273	DNA repair protein Rad51 homolog-like Protein
	TC006656	659938	Calmodulin-like Protein
	TC007015	655573	
	TC007136	663031	Muscle LIM protein Mlp84B-like Protein
	TC008043	661043	Nidogen-2-like Protein
	TC008058	662217	Cytochrome P450-like protein
	TC008838	664378	Pox meso
	TC010415	100141749	Zinc finger protein 585B-like Protein
	TC010484	657683	
	TC011075	655583	Protein flightless-1-like Protein
	TC011101	656912	Cuticular protein analogous to neurotrophins 1-J
	TC011461	656904	Tropomyosin-2-like Protein
	TC011769	663556	Myosin regulatory light chain 2-like Protein
	TC012196	659195	Troponin C, isoform 1-like Protein
	TC012671	658328	Calcium-transporting ATPase
	TC012704	662809	Troponin C, isoform 2-like Protein
	TC013627	657022	
	TC014609	656064	Glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
	TC014640	659140	Actin-binding Rho-activating protein-like Protein
	TC014770	657728	Pupal cuticle protein Edg-78E-like Protein
	TC015855	660723	Myogenic-determination protein-like Protein
	TC032290	660703	
	TC032995	103313393	Peroxisome biogenesis factor 2-like Protein
	TC034748	659141	